

“FLIPPED CLASSROOM” METHOD AND ITS ADVANTAGES

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Abstract

The "Flipped Classroom" is a pedagogical model that inverts traditional teaching methods by delivering instructional content, often online, outside of the classroom. Instead of the conventional model where students learn new content in class and then complete assignments at home, the flipped classroom approach has students engage with new material at home, typically through video lectures or readings, and use classroom time for interactive, hands-on activities. This model shifts the focus of learning from passive reception of information to active participation and problem-solving, fostering deeper understanding and application of concepts.

The origins of the flipped classroom can be traced back to the early 2000s, with its rise in popularity due to its potential to cater to diverse learning styles and paces. Allowing students to absorb new information at their speed outside of class enables more personalized and student-centred learning experiences during in-class time. The successful implementation of this model requires adequate technological infrastructure and a shift in both student and teacher roles, where students take more responsibility for their learning, and teachers act as facilitators rather than sole providers of knowledge.

Despite challenges such as the digital divide and the need for teacher training, the flipped classroom model has demonstrated significant potential in enhancing student engagement, improving comprehension, and preparing students for real-world problem-solving. It has been particularly effective in STEM education and is being adopted in various educational levels increasingly and contexts worldwide.

Keywords: flipped classroom, active learning, educational technology, classroom interaction, digital resources, homework and in-class activities, pedagogical innovation, critical thinking, STEM Education.

Introduction

We live in a time where technology is developing rapidly. As in all fields, it is possible to apply new technologies in education and achieve high results. One of the models created in education with the application of new technology is the "Flipped classroom" model. Suppose we pay attention to the students around us. In that case, they constantly use phones, the Internet, computers, and tablets, and for a student who is in so much contact with technology every day, solving a task in a notebook and reading the subject only from a book can be somewhat depressing. Undoubtedly, the student's

learning depends on his motivation and attitude towards education. One of the main goals in the implementation of the "Flipped classroom" model is to ensure that students use phones and computers, which are a part of their lives, for educational purposes, which will be more useful for them.

In traditional training, the teacher transfers information to the students in the classroom. It is more difficult to master and apply it, and it is assigned to the student himself through homework. Very few students can cope with this difficult task because it is really difficult for them to apply what they have learned from the subject without a teacher. (1)

The "Flipped Classroom" represents a transformative approach to education that challenges the traditional model of teaching. In conventional classrooms, students receive instruction during class time and complete assignments or further exploration at home. However, the flipped classroom inverts this process, having students first encounter new material outside of class, often through digital resources like videos, readings, or podcasts. Classroom time is then dedicated to deeper exploration of the content including discussions, collaborative projects, and practical applications.

This process model is reversed in the "Flipped classroom". If we pay attention to its literal meaning "Flipped classroom" means a turned class. Unlike the traditional system, in the "Flipped classroom" model information is given to the student at home and its assimilation and application are carried out in the classroom. (2)

This model emerged in the early 21st century as educators sought to leverage advancements in technology to enhance student learning. The flipped classroom approach is rooted in the belief that students can benefit from engaging with instructional material at their own pace before coming to class, where they can then apply what they have learned with the guidance and support of their teacher and peers.

The focus from passive reception to active engagement, the flipped classroom seeks to foster a more personalized and interactive learning experience by shifting. It encourages students to take greater responsibility for their education while enabling teachers to provide more targeted support. As this model gains traction, it continues to reshape educational practices, offering new opportunities for enhancing student understanding and success across various disciplines.

The "Flipped Classroom" is an innovative educational model that serves as an alternative to traditional teaching methods. In this approach, the learning process is "flipped," meaning that students are introduced to new content at home, typically through videos, articles, or other digital resources, and then spend class time engaging in discussions, problem-solving activities, and practical applications of the material.

Key Features:

1. **Learning location is reversed:** Students learn new content at home before coming to class, which allows them to process information at their own pace. This is usually done through videos, readings, or other online resources.

2. **Class time is more interactive:** In the classroom, the teacher focuses on deepening understanding through discussions, answering questions, and facilitating group work. This allows for a more interactive and engaging learning experience.

3. **Increased student responsibility:** Students are expected to come to class prepared, having already familiarized themselves with the material. This encourages active participation and deeper engagement during class.

Advantages of the Flipped Classroom:

- **Self-paced learning:** Students can learn their speed by reviewing difficult concepts as needed.

- **Development of essential skills:** Classroom activities promote critical thinking, communication, and collaboration skills among students.

- **Enhanced teacher-student interaction:** More time is available for personalized support, as teachers can address individual needs and questions during class.

The Flipped Classroom model leverages modern technology to create more effective and engaging educational experiences, and it has gained popularity in recent years.

History and Development

If we look at the history of this method we can see that it was first introduced in 1993 by the writer Alison King in her book "Sage on the Stage to Guide on the Side", drawing attention to the safety of using class time to understand many topics better that meet the requirements during class. Although she did not deal with the concept of the Flipped Classroom in this book, King's work provided impetus for the proposal of this method in the field of education.

With this, the search for a strategy that would meet the needs of every student with different learning methods with the available technical capabilities over the years was started. In some universities in the United States in 2000, conditions were created to record classes in video form. These conditions began to reveal the further usefulness of this method for students. (2)

The "Flipped Classroom" model became widespread in the early 2000s popularized by two chemistry teachers Jonathan Bergmann and Aaron Sams. They proposed the idea of having students watch lessons at home and dedicating classroom time to more interactive activities. Initially applied in middle and high schools, this approach soon gained popularity in universities and other educational institutions.

Bergman and Sams observed that school students who were forced to participate in sports competitions found it difficult to make up for the gaps in lessons when they missed classes. One day, Sams comes across a program in a technology magazine that he can make in video format by playing PowerPoint presentations. Both teachers decide to prepare a video tutorial for sports and students who cannot attend classes for various reasons.

By uploading the videos they prepared to the Internet, students who cannot attend classes can study the lessons they missed. These videos soon attract the interest of other students, and the students participating in the classes also start watching the videos. Thus, by watching these videos again and again, students could learn the points they did not understand in the lesson and reinforce what they learned. They even used these videos when preparing for the exam. The fame of this method soon began to spread in the educational institutions of the country and it started to be used in different schools and by different teachers.

At the end of this experiment, Sams suggests that the curriculum be reviewed and updated. He advocates that students can learn independently at home through these videos and work with teachers on more practical tasks and issues during class. Finally, he is able to convince and this method is added to the curriculum. This is how the Flipped Classroom method is born. During the trial period of 1 year, this method gives successful results and becomes popular by appearing on news channels. The name “Flipped Classroom” is also a name given by the local media.

Apparently, this method reverses the lecture format, which is considered a traditional compressive method for requirements. Students have the opportunity to watch the explanation of each new lesson a day in advance with a video tutorial prepared by teachers. As a result, unclear points are explained to them during the live lesson, their questions are answered, and their knowledge is strengthened by working on more practical problems and projects. (2)

Typical Structure of the Flipped Classroom Model

1. **Homework (Lesson Preparation):** Students review assigned materials at home (video lessons, articles, podcasts, etc.), which allows them to learn the core concepts at their own pace.

2. **In-Class Activities:**

Discussions and Analysis: Classroom discussions help students deepen their understanding of the material they have studied.

Problem Solving: Students work on individual or group assignments in class, applying concepts and addressing real-world problems.

Teacher Interaction: The teacher provides individual support during class, answering questions and explaining complex topics.

Technologies Supporting the Flipped Classroom Model

The effective implementation of this model relies on various technologies:

Video Platforms: Platforms like YouTube, Vimeo, and specialized educational platforms provide ample opportunities for students to watch lessons at home.

Learning Management Systems: Systems like Moodle and Google Classroom help track student activities and share assignments.

Interactive Tools: Programs like Kahoot and Quizlet can be used to test students’ understanding of the material.

Challenges in Implementing the Flipped Classroom

Student Independence: Not all students are equally capable of learning at their own pace, which can lead to difficulties in class.

Technological Barriers: The lack of necessary technological resources at home can hinder the implementation of this model.

Teacher Preparation: Teachers require additional training and resources to apply this model effectively.

Success Stories of the Flipped Classroom Model

There are numerous examples of the successful implementation of this model. For instance, in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) fields students use this method to better understand complex topics. The Flipped Classroom Model has been applied in higher education successfully and in corporate training programs.

Conclusion

The “Flipped Classroom” model has proven to be a significant innovation in modern education, offering a dynamic alternative to traditional teaching methods. By reversing the conventional structure of in-class instruction followed by homework, it emphasizes active learning and student engagement. This approach allows students to absorb content at their pace also maximizes classroom time for interactive, hands-on activities that reinforce and deepen their understanding.

While the model presents challenges, such as the need for technological resources and the shift in both teaching and learning dynamics, its benefits are evident in fostering critical thinking, collaboration, and practical problem-solving skills. The flipped classroom aligns well with the needs of 21st-century learners, preparing them for real-world challenges by promoting self-directed learning and enabling teachers to act as facilitators rather than mere transmitters of knowledge.

As educational institutions continue to explore and refine this approach, the flipped classroom has the potential to significantly enhance the effectiveness of teaching and learning, making education more personalized, engaging, and adaptable to the needs of diverse learners.

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